

“A Review On Plants Having Anthelmintic Efficacy”

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Abstract

Background: Bangladesh is endowed with abundant medicinal plant resources and traditional medicinal practices. However, available research evidence on indigenous anthelmintic plants are highly fragmented in the country. The present systematic review attempted to explore, synthesize and compile ethno-medicinal research evidence on anthelmintic medicinal plants available in Bangladesh.

Methods: A systematic web search analysis and review was conducted on research literature pertaining to medicinal plants used for traditional helminthic treatment on worldwide. Data were collected from a total of 134 different studies meeting specific inclusion criteria including published research articles and unpublished thesis reports. Relevant ethno-botanical/medicinal information using descriptive comparison, percentage, tables, and bar graphs.

Results: Analysis of ethno-medicinal recipes indicated that mainly fresh leaves were used for preparation of remedies. Decoction, concoction and eating/chewing were found to be the most frequently employed herbal remedy preparation methods.

Conclusion: The study highlighted different indigenous anthelmintic medicinal plants with equally divergent herbal remedy preparation and use pattern on worldwide. Likewise, herbal remedy toxicity risks and countermeasures generally entailed more exhaustive investigation. Experimental research and advanced chemical analysis are also required to validate the therapeutic potential of anthelmintic compounds from promising plant species.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1.1.Introduction:

Since ages, humans have relied on nature for their basic needs for the production of foodstuff, shelters, clothing, means of transportation, fertilizers, flavors, and fragrances, and not the least, medicines. Plants have formed the basis of sophisticated traditional systems of medicine that have been in existence for thousands of years and continue to provide humankind with new remedies. ^[1].

1.Early humans acquired the knowledge on plant utilization for therapeutic values through many years of vigilant observations, experience, and trial and error experiments^[2].

2.Traditional medicinal plants are an important element of indigenous medical systems in China and rest of the world. ^[3].

3. Traditional medicine refers to any ancient and culturally based health care practice differing from scientific medicine and is largely transmitted orally by communities of different cultures. ^[4].

4. Traditional system of medicine is one of the centuries-old practice and long-serving companion to humankind in the fight against disease and in leading a healthy life. Indigenous people have been using the unique approach of their traditional system of medicine for centuries and among the most renowned are the Chinese, Indian, African systems of medicine. ^[5].

5. Traditional medicinal plants are readily available and culturally acceptable. They offer an accessible and affordable health care regime and serve as an important source of livelihood for indigenous rural populations^[6].

6. Research on plant and use of traditional medicinal information has again received considerable interest. Indeed, herbal medicine is an integral part of any traditional system of medicine, and the present review becomes more significant from this viewpoint.

The main objective of the present review is to explore the significance of traditional system of medicine, in particular traditional medicinal plants as a primary health care modality in developing and resource-poor countries. It is also an endeavor to identify the existing major challenges and the opportunities to preserve this age-old precious gift of nature to humankind. Definitions Traditional Medicine The World Health Organization (WHO, 2002) ^[7] observes that it is difficult to assign one definition to the broad range of characteristics and elements of traditional medicine, but that a working definition is essential. It thus concludes that the traditional medicines diverse health

practices, approaches, knowledge and beliefs incorporating plant, animal and/or mineral based medicines, spiritual therapies, manual techniques and exercises applied singularly or in combination to maintain well-being, as well as to treat, diagnose or prevent illness.’’

Complementary/Alternative Medicine The terms complementary medicine and alternative medicine are used interchangeably with traditional medicine in some countries. They refer to a broad set of health care practices that are not part of that country’s own tradition and are not integrated into the dominant health care system.

African Traditional Medicine

One of the definitions given for African traditional medicine by the WHO Centre for Health Development is the following: The sum of all knowledge and practices, whether explicable or not, used in diagnosis, prevention and elimination of physical, mental, or societal imbalance, and relying exclusively on practical experience and observation handed down from generation to generation, whether verbally or in writing. Medicinal Plant According to the WHO, ^[9]. “*a medicinal plant is plant which, in one or more of its organs, contains substance that can be used for therapeutic purposes, or which are precursors for chemopharmaceutical semi-synthesis.*”

Herb

An herb in the botanical sense is a plant lacking a permanent woody stem that produces seeds and flowers and that dies down after its growing season. In a culinary or gardening sense, these materials possess, in addition, strong flavors and fragrances and therefore make foods more attractive to consume. These definitions are broader than that applied in traditional medical systems. In a traditional medical sense, an herb is a small and non woody plant valued for its medicinal, savory, or aromatic qualities. An herbal preparation is, then, a natural remedy derived from herbs.

Significance of Traditional Medicine and Complementary/Alternative Medicine:

Despite globalization and modernization, a sizable fraction of the rural poor purely rely on the traditional medicines as their primary health care modality. ^[10]. The dependence on traditional medicinal plants and their role in health care system will only increase in the future as they are culturally viable and expected to remain affordable and because the existing modern health care service is limited and expensive compared with traditional medicine. ^[11]. Traditional system of medicine has been the only option available for health care prior to the induction of modern

medicine for prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of social, mental, and physical illness.^[12]

Renaissance of Traditional Medicine and Complementary/Alternative Medicine

Indeed, the induction of modern health care services has posed immense threat to indigenous health practices because of their potential and speedy therapeutic effect. This has led to the disappearance and displacement of traditional systems of medicine. Also, traditional systems are undervalued by the people^[13]. However, the rise in population, inadequate supply of drugs, prohibitive cost of treatments, side effects of several allopathic drugs, and development of resistance to currently used drugs for infectious diseases have led to increased emphasis on the use of plant materials as a source of medicine for a wide variety of human ailments.^[14] Globally, there is a resurgence of traditional system of medicine because of its user-friendly nature and because of the intrinsic side effects of modern medicines.^[15] Over the past 3 decades, the scientific community worldwide is extremely inclined toward longstanding traditional systems of medicine to explore the opportunities to formulate novel phytotherapeutic agents^[10].

Traditional Medicinal Plants

Of the 2,50,000 higher plant species on earth, more than 80,000 species are reported to have at least some medicinal value.^{20,21} There are about 400 families in the world of flowering plants, of which at least 315 are represented in India. According to WHO, approximately 21,000 plant species have the potential for being used as medicinal plants.¹⁴ Although some of the therapeutic properties attributed to plants have been proven to be erroneous,¹ the use of traditional medicinal plants for the treatment of various diseases is well known and documented since ancient times. .^[6]

According to Jiexiang^[10] 4877 plant species belongs to different plant groups having potential therapeutic value. Plants have been used as medicines throughout history. Indeed, studies of wild animals show that they also instinctively eat certain plants to treat themselves of certain illnesses. Medicinal plants are widely and successfully used on every continent. In Asia, the practice of herbal medicine is well established and documented. As a result, most of the medicinal plants that have international recognition come from this region, particularly from China and India. In Europe and North America, the use of herbal medicine is increasing rapidly, especially for correcting imbalances caused by modern diets and lifestyles. In Africa, attitudes toward traditional herbal medicines vary widely.

History of Traditional and Folk Herbal Medicine

The use of plants as medicine goes back to the period of early humans. Fossil records date human use of plants as medicines at least to the Middle Paleolithic age. Evidences of this early association have been found in the grave of a Neanderthal man buried 60,000 years ago. The earliest known medical document is a 4000-year-old Sumerian clay tablet that recorded plant remedies for various illnesses. By the time of the ancient Egyptian civilization, a great wealth of information already existed on medicinal plants. This information, along with the hundreds of other remedies, has been preserved in the Ebers papyrus for nearly 3500 years^[4,14]. Ancient China is also a source of information about the early medicinal uses of plants. The *Pun-tsaio*, a pharmacopoeia that was actually published around 1600 BC, contained thousands of herbal cures that are attributed to the works of Shen-nung, China's legendary emperor who lived more than 4500 years ago.^[10] The development of systematic pharmacopoeias dates back to 3000 BC, when the Chinese were already using more than 350 herbal remedies. China has demonstrated the best use of traditional medicine in providing health care. Ayurveda, a system of herbal medicines widely practiced in India, Sri Lanka, and Southeast Asia has more than 8000 plant remedies and uses nearly 35 000 to 70 000 plant species^[20]. Among the ancient civilizations, India has been known to be the richest repository of medicinal plants. About 8000 herbal remedies have been codified in Ayurveda. The *Rigveda* (5000 BC) has recorded 67 medicinal plants, the *Yajurveda* 81 species, the *Atharvaveda* (4500-2500 BC) 290 species, and the *Charak Samhita* (700 BC) and *Sushrut Samhita* (200 BC) have described properties and uses of 1100 and 1270 species, respectively, to compound the drugs and use. They are still used in the classical formulations of medicine in the Ayurvedic system of medicine. One useful plant from Ayurveda knowledge is snakeroot or *Rauwolfia serpentina*, which has been in use for centuries together for its sedative effects. Today the active components in snakeroot are widely used in Western medicine too to effectively treat high blood pressure. Plants used in organized traditional medical systems such as Ayurveda, Unani, Kampo, and traditional Chinese medicine have flourished as systems of medicine for thousands of years. These systems are still in place today because of their organizational strength and because they focus primarily on multicomponent mixtures^[31,32,33].

In other parts of the world, medicinal plants are also important elements of indigenous medical systems. For example, in the northwestern Amazon, indigenous people use at least 1300 plant species to create *drogas do certaõ* or "wildness drugs." In Southeast Asia, traditional healers use 6500 different types of plants to treat malaria, stomach ulcers, syphilis, and other disorders.^[39] Herbs are staging a comeback and herbal "renaissance" is happening all over the globe. Herbal products today symbolize safety in contrast to the synthetics that are regarded as unsafe for humans and the

environment. Although herbs have been prized for their medicinal, flavoring, and aromatic qualities for centuries, the synthetic products of the modern age surpassed their importance.^[41]The focus is now on replacing chemical substances with plant-derived ones.^[29]Patients use traditional medicine for many reasons. They may be from a remote area where modern medicine is not available when they need it. They may belong to communities whose habits and treatment-seeking behavior resorts to traditional medicine as the first choice. They may prefer traditional medicine believing, for example, that they produce fewer side effects or cures them more effectively. They may have experienced a failure with a modern treatment and want to try traditional methods. They may want to avoid modern health facilities because they perceive them as expensive, unfriendly, dangerous, or ridden with corruption. Patients may also avoid modern drugs sold on the market because they are aware of the fact that many of them are counterfeit or “fake” drugs.

Major Challenges and Opportunities in Developing Traditional Medicine and Complementary/Alternative Medicine Care :

The safety, efficacy, policy, access, rational use, and quality control of traditional medicine and complementary/alternative medicine have become important concerns for both health authorities and the public. To maximize the potential of traditional medicine and complementary/alternative medicine as a source of potential health care, a number of issues must first be tackled. Relatively few countries, only 25 among WHO’s 191 member states, have developed a policy on traditional medicine and/or complementary and alternative medicine^[45]. Traditional knowledge built on the long experiences of people was adopted in social, economic, environmental, spiritual, and political practices. Since traditional knowledge is developed through a long process of trial and error, this could guide search for new drugs. Together with the recognition of the importance of the traditional knowledge, serious concern about the loss of knowledge can be observed in the past few years throughout the world.^[43,44]

Traditional Knowledge: So Precious to Preserve

Traditional plant usage custom is a result of thousands of years of experience. This expertise has been passed down to many generations chiefly through verbal means. This mode of transfer of information can result in distortion or loss of indigenous knowledge and usage custom of the plants. The knowledge of traditional healing practices mainly by the use of wild plants is now fast disappearing because of modernization, globalization, and the tendency to change traditional lifestyles. Ethnic groups are the repositories of the knowledge on herbal remedy and these need to be documented and tapped properly^[30]. The loss of traditional medicinal plants because of

natural and anthropogenic factors is related to the loss of valuable indigenous knowledge associated with these plants.^[38] This strong link suggests a need to conduct ethnobotanical research and to document the medicinal plants and the associated indigenous knowledge. These studies are extremely useful to identify endangered medicinal plant species and to take appropriate conservation measures in the near future.

Modernization: A Threat :

The most serious threat to existing knowledge and practice on traditional medicinal plants include cultural change, particularly the influence of modernization and lack of interest shown by the younger generations. These were the main problems reported by the informants during the field survey.^[47] Hence, the proper documentation of the use of traditional medicinal plants as phytotherapeutic agents and the related indigenous knowledge held by the tribal community is inevitably required to preserve our traditional knowledge.

Dearth of Scientific Knowledge: Need to Explore:

People who use traditional remedies may not understand the scientific rationale behind their medicines, but they know from personal experience that some medicinal plants can be highly effective if used at therapeutic doses. Since we have a better understanding today of how the body functions, we are in a better position to understand the healing powers of plants and their potential as multifunctional chemical entities for treating complicated health conditions. Medicinal plants typically contain mixtures of different chemical compounds that may act individually, additively, or in synergy to improve health.

Lack of Standardization on Safety, Efficacy, and Quality in Traditional Medicine and Complementary/Alternative Medicine Care:

In industrialized nations, herbal medicine is now a multibillion dollar industry, and in developing countries, up to 80% of people rely on plant-based medicines. The identity, authenticity, and quality of crude plants are often uncertain and difficult to assess. The quality of manufactured products varies considerably worldwide, and regulations can be complex or inadequate. Standardization is possible for the few herbs for which all active ingredients are known (panel), but is technically difficult and would make drugs unaffordable in developing nations.

Safety

In general, traditional procedure-based therapies are relatively safe, if they are performed properly by well-trained practitioners. But accidents do occasionally occur, most probably when practitioners are not fully trained. Therapies should be performed within accepted parameters, and the indications for a therapy should be evidence based when possible. Serious adverse effects of therapies are rare, but supportive data on adverse effects are not readily available. Accordingly, the evaluation of adverse effects should be considered a priority area for systematic evaluation of safety of these therapies^[25]. The active ingredients used in many traditional medicines are potentially toxic, often containing dangerous elements and can include heavy metals.^[47] Even the use of ineffective nontoxic remedies can be harmful if it delays effective treatment. For instance, fears have been expressed that, in Nigeria, witchcraft and traditional remedies of unknown efficacy are widely employed as treatments for malaria to delay the access to modern medicines of proven effectiveness.^[39-42]

Efficacy

Traditional medicines are currently under scrutiny to evaluate their effectiveness and to monitor their adverse effects^[47]. Such analyses have often failed to confirm the efficacy of traditional remedies: For instance, of nearly 25 000 applications for registration of traditional medicines received by Malaysian authorities, 37.3% were rejected, either on grounds of safety or ineffectiveness.^[33] However, there is currently no compelling explanation for the prevalence of low-efficacy treatments. . Traditional and complementary and alternative medicine practices have developed within different cultures in different regions. So there has been no parallel development of standards and methods, either nationally or internationally, for evaluating them^[46,47].

Quality

Although widely used, the efficacy of many herbal drugs is unproven. Moreover, many consumers misinterpret the natural origin of herbal medicines as a sign of safety, without appreciating the fact that herbal ingredients can also cause serious adverse effects^[46]. Therefore, herbal medicines should be assessed with randomized controlled trials. For example, in Ghana, majority of the people administer plant products in the form of decoction; however, none of the people interviewed provided proper information about how they might “standardize” treatments, and it has been observed that the amounts used by them were generally vague. Thus the quality could vary greatly between prescriptions. This lack of standardization and quality control is seen

as one of the major disadvantages of traditional/complementary and alternative medicine. In the traditional system of medicine, some plant species are also used as mixtures, which makes it more complex to standardize, investigate, and monitor the levels of biologically active compounds. Therefore, efficient quality control methods need to be developed.^[47]

Conservation of Medicinal Plants

Medicinal plants are threatened by anthropogenic activities, since these plants have several other useful applications, for example, as timber, fuel, and construction poles^[42]. It is necessary to initiate systematic cultivation of medicinal plants in order to conserve biodiversity and protect endangered species. In the pharmaceutical industry, where the active medicinal principle cannot be synthesized economically, the product must be obtained from the cultivation of plants^[43]. Sustainable management of medicinal plant species is important, not only because of their value as a potential source of new drugs but also because of the reliance on medicinal plants for health care^[44]. Systematic conservation and large scale cultivation of the concerned medicinal plants are thus of great importance. Efforts are also required to suggest appropriate cropping patterns for the incorporation of these plants into conventional agricultural and forestry cropping systems^[45].

Decisively, despite its existence and continued use over many centuries, and its popularity and extensive use during the past decade, traditional medicine has not been officially recognized in most countries. Consequently, education, training, and research in this area have not been accorded due attention and support. The quantity and quality of the safety and efficacy data on traditional medicine are far from sufficient to meet the criteria needed to support its use worldwide. The reasons for the lack of research data are not only health care policies but also a lack of adequate or accepted research methodology for evaluating traditional medicine. It should also be noted that there are published and unpublished data on research in traditional medicine in various countries, but further research on safety and efficacy should be promoted, and the quality of the research should be improved.

Ref:Traditional Medicinal Plants: A Source of Phytotherapeutic Modality in Resource-Constrained Health Care Settings

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1.1.2 Background:

The term parasite (Latin parasites – Greek παρασιτῶσ-parasitos, παρα- (para-, beside) + σιτῶσ(sitos, wheat, food) “person who eats at the table of the bystander” “feeding beside”) is employed here in the traditional sense, but it must be stated that such concepts are only communication tools to be used in a flexible and relative way, as are the biological phenomena.

The term “cohabitant” is often more accurate than parasite, because it is increasingly clear that every living being, from bacteria to mammals, is a consortium of living beings . Even we propose that the term parasitology should be replaced by Cohabitation because there is no parasite and host alone: both together compose a new adaptive system: the parasitized-host or the cohabitant-cohabited being . Symbiosis is a cyclical and permanent phenomenon in evolution .

During our relatively short history on Earth, humans have acquired an amazing number of parasites, about 300 species of helminth worms and over 70 species of protozoa . Many of these are rare and accidental parasites, but we still harbor about 90 relatively common species, of which a small proportion cause some of the most important diseases in the world, inevitably, these are the ones that have received the most attention. Since most of these parasitic diseases occur mainly in the tropics, the field of parasitology has tended to overlap with that of tropical medicine, and thus the histories of these two fields are intertwined. ^[48].

HUMAN EVOLUTION, MIGRATIONS, CIVILIZATION, AND PARASITIC INFECTIONS

Human evolution and parasitic infections have run hand in hand, and thanks to the spinoffs from the Human Genome Project, we now know much more about the origins of the human race than ever before . Sometime, about 150,000 years ago, *Homo sapiens* emerged in eastern Africa and spread throughout the world, possibly in several waves , until 15,000 years ago at the end of the Ice Age humans had migrated to and inhabited virtually the whole of the face of the Earth, bringing some parasites with them and collecting others on the way. For the purpose of this review, the parasites that infect humans can be classified as heirlooms or souvenirs. Heirlooms are the parasites inherited from our primate ancestors in Africa, and souvenirs are those that we have acquired from the animals with which we have come in contact during our evolution, migrations, and agricultural practices. The development of settlements and cities facilitated the transmission of infections between humans, and the opening up of trade routes resulted in the wider

dissemination of parasitic infections. The slave trade, which flourished for three and a half centuries from about 1500, brought new parasites to the New World from the Old World ; in more recent times, the spread of human immunodeficiency virus HIV and AIDS and the immunodepression associated with these conditions has resulted in the establishment of a number of new opportunistic parasitic infections throughout the world [49-52].

EARLY WRITTEN RECORDS

The first written records of what are almost certainly parasitic infections come from a period of Egyptian medicine from 3000 to 400 BC, particularly the Ebers papyrus of 1500 BC discovered at Thebes . Later, there were many detailed descriptions of various diseases that might or might not be caused by parasites, specifically fevers, in the writings of Greek physicians between 800 to 300 BC, such as the collected works of Hippocrates, known as the *Corpus Hippocraticorum*, and from physicians from other civilizations including China from 3000 to 300 BC, India from 2500 to 200 BC, Rome from 700 BC to 400 AD, and the Arab Empire in the latter part of the first millennium. As time passed, the descriptions of infections became more accurate and Arabic physicians, particularly Rhazes (AD 850 to 923) and Avicenna (AD 980 to 1037) , wrote important medical works that contain a great deal of information about diseases clearly caused by parasites.

In Europe, the Dark and Middle Ages, characterized by religious and superstitious beliefs, held back medical progress until the Renaissance, which released a flurry of activity that eventually led to the great discoveries that characterized the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th. These discoveries included the demolition of the theory of spontaneous generation and the evolution of the germ theory by Louis Pasteur, the demonstration by Pasteur that diseases could be caused by bacteria, the discovery of viruses by Pierre-Paul Emile Roux, the introduction by Robert Koch of methods of preventing diseases caused by microorganisms, and the incrimination by Patrick Manson of vectors in the transmission of parasites. The great personalities of this period made discoveries in a number of fields, and their findings and ideas fed off one another. The names of Pasteur, Koch, Roux, and Manson occur time and time again in the history of parasitology and microbiology^[53].

DISCOVERY OF THE HELMINTH WORMS

Because of the large size of some helminths, such as the roundworm *Ascaris* and the tapeworms, it is practically certain that our earliest ancestors must have been aware of these common worms. There is some evidence for this assumption based on contemporary studies of primitive tribes in Sarawak and North Borneo, where

Hoeppli found that most people are aware of their intestinal roundworms and tapeworms. Some historians have identified references to helminth worms and their diseases in the Bible, but the relevant passages are open to several interpretations. Among the Egyptian medical papyri, the Ebers papyrus refers to intestinal worms, and these records can be confirmed by the discovery of calcified helminth eggs in mummies dating from 1200 BC. The Greeks, particularly Hippocrates (460 to 375 BC), knew about worms from fishes, domesticated animals, and humans. Roman physicians including Celsus (25 BC to AD 50) and Galen (Galenus of Pergamon, AD 129 to 200) were familiar with the human roundworms *Ascaris lumbricoides* and *Enterobius vermicularis* and tapeworms belonging to the genus *Taenia*. Somewhat later, Paulus Aegineta (AD 625 to 690) clearly described *Ascaris*, *Enterobius*, and tapeworms and gave good clinical descriptions of the infections they caused. Following the decline of the Roman Empire, the study of medicine switched to Arabic physicians, including Avicenna, who recognized not only *Ascaris*, *Enterobius*, and tapeworms but also the guinea worm, *Dracunculus medinensis*, which had been recorded in parts of the Arab world, particularly around the Red Sea, for over 1,000 years.

The medical literature of the Middle Ages is very limited, but there are many references to parasitic worms. In some cases, they were recognized as the possible causes of disease but in general, the writings of the period reflect the culture, beliefs, and ignorance of the time. The science of helminthology really took off in the 17th and 18th centuries following the reemergence of science and scholarship during the Renaissance period. Linnaeus described and named six helminth worms, *Ascaris lumbricoides*, *Ascaris vermicularis* (= *Enterobius vermicularis*), *Gordius medinensis* (= *Dracunculus medinensis*), *Fasciola hepatica*, *Taenia solium*, and *Taenia lata* (= *Diphyllobothrium latum*). Thereafter, more species were described until at the beginning of the 20th century, 28 species had been recorded in humans, a number that has now grown to about 300 species, including accidental and very rare records. Even if some of these are doubtful, at least 280 species are recognized by Ashford and Crewe in their annotated checklist. Some of the most important helminthes and their related diseases that are prevailing in our society are as follows:

1. *Ascaris* and Ascariasis
2. Hookworms and Hookworm Disease
3. *Trichinella* and Trichinosis
4. *Strongyloides* and Strongyloidiasis
5. *Dracunculus* and Dracunculiasis (Guinea Worm Disease)
6. Filarial Worms and Lymphatic Filariasis (Elephantiasis)
7. *Loa* and Loiasis (Eye Worm) and *Onchocerca* and

8. Onchocerciasis (River Blindness)
9. Schistosomes and Schistosomiasis
10. Liver and Lung Fluke Diseases
11. Cestodiasis (Tapeworm Infections)
12. South American Trypanosomiasis: Chagas' Disease
13. Toxoplasma, Toxoplasmosis, and Infections Caused by Related Organisms

(Ref: History of Human Parasitology-F. E. G. Cox*)

Summary:

Table: Some important helminthic infections in human.

METAZOA

Nematoda

Filarioidea

<i>Wucheria bancrofti</i>	Lymphatic	Mosquitos (<i>Aedes</i> ,	Tropical	Infection of lymphatic system;
<i>Brugia spp.</i>	filariases,	<i>Culex, Mansonia</i>);	Africa,	enlargement of lymph nodes
<i>Mansonella spp.</i>	Elephantiasis	Bites	Asia,	
	(120 million)		America	
<i>Loa loa</i>	Loaiasis	<i>Chrysops</i>	Central	Female worms migrate through tissues
	(33 million)		Africa	and the eye
<i>Onchocerca volvulus</i>	Skin filariases;	Flies	Mostly	Formation of large nodules under skin
	onchocerciasis;	(<i>Simulium spp.</i>);	tropical	or in eyes (causing blindness)
	river blindness	Bites	Africa and	
	(>17 million)		America	

Trichuroidea

<i>Trichinella spiralis</i>	Trichinosis	Eating of infected	Worldwide	Invades muscular tissue, fever,
	(50 million)	muscles e.g., from		myalgia, malaise and oedema
		pigs; bites		

<i>Trichurus trichiura</i>	(500 million)	Infection from contaminated soil	Worldwide	Intestinal infection
<hr/>				
<hr/>				
Parasite	Disease (estimated number of infections)	Vector (hosts); route of Transmission	Distribution	Symptoms
<hr/>				
Rhabditoidea				
<i>Strongyloides</i>	Strongyloidiasis	Infection from contaminated soil	Subtropics, tropics	Intestinal infection, migrating larvae in skin
<i>Stercoralis</i>	(70 million)		worldwide	
<hr/>				
Ancylostomatoidea				
<i>Ancylostoma duodenale</i> ; <i>Necator americanus</i>	Hookworm Infection (700–900 million)	Infection from contaminated soil	Subtropics, tropics	Intestinal infection, migrating larvae in skin
<hr/>				
Oxyuroidea				
<i>Enterobius</i> <i>Vermicularis</i>	Thread or Pinworm	Infection from contaminated	Worldwide	Intestinal infection
<hr/>				
Ascaridoidea				
<i>Ascaris lumbricoides</i>	Ascariasis (800–1000 million)	Infection from contaminated soil	Worldwide	Intestinal infection, migrating larvae in various tissues
<hr/>				
Dracunculoidea				
<i>Dracunculus medinensis</i>	Dracunculiasis; guinea worm Infection(≤3 million)	Copepods as intermediate host	Africa, Asia	Infects skin; female worms can reach a length of 100 cm
<hr/>				

Plathelminthes

Trematoda				
Schistosomatoidea				
<i>Schistosoma mansoni</i>	Schistosomiasis	Water snails as intermediate host	Tropical and subtropical Africa, S America and E Asia	Dermatitis, infects liver, granuloma formation in liver, liver fibrosis, enlarged spleen
<i>S. japonicum</i>	(200 million)			
<i>S. haematobium</i>	Schistosomiasis	Water snails as intermediate host	Africa	Infection of bladder, haematuria
	(80 million)			
Echinostomatoidea				
<i>Fasciola hepatica</i>	Fasciolopsiasis	Water snail	Worldwide	Infection of liver
<i>F. gigantica</i>	(2.4 million)	(<i>Lymnaea</i>) as host		
Opisthorchioidea				
<i>Opisthorchis felineus</i>	Opisthorchiasis,	Water snails as intermediate host;	E Europe, Central and	Infection of liver and gall bladder
<i>O. viverrini</i>	liver fluke	infection from infected fish	Eastern Asia	
	(10 million)			

(Ref: Medicinal Plants: A Source of Anti-Parasitic Secondary Metabolites - Michael Wink)

Anthelmintic drugs and its discovery:

Many anthelmintic drugs used to treat humans were first developed and marketed as veterinary drugs [70]. There are only a few classes of anthelmintics including; benzimidazoles, imidazothiazoles, tetrahydropyrimidines, macrocyclic lactones, amino-acetonitrile derivatives, spiroindoles and cyclooctadepsipeptides.

Benzimidazoles (BZs)

Thiabendazole was the first benzimidazole anthelmintic agent produced. Since the introduction of thiabendazole in 1961, a number of benzimidazoles with improved efficacy and extended spectrum of action have been developed [71]. These include mebendazole, albendazole and flubendazole (Figure 1). The initial mode of action of benzimidazoles was thought to be inhibition of various parasite metabolic enzymes including fumarate reductase and malate dehydrogenase [72]. However, it is now established that benzimidazoles selectively bind with high affinity to parasite β -tubulin and inhibit microtubule polymerization. This results in the destruction of cell structure and consequent death of the parasite [73].

Figure 1. Chemical structures of thiabendazole (A), mebendazole (B), albendazole (C) and flubendazole (D). From ^[74].

Imidazothiazoles

Imidazothiazoles act as nicotinic acetylcholine receptor (nAChR) agonists. They bind to nAChRs on body wall muscles, causing spastic paralysis of the worm, and hence, its expulsion from the host ^[75]. Tetramisole (Figure 2), an aminothiazol derivative, was the first member of this class of anthelmintics, and constitutes a racemic mixture of 50% L- or S- and D- or R-isomers [76]. The L-isomer was later demonstrated to be more potent than the racemic mixture or the D-isomer ^[81,82]. Consequently, the D-isomer was removed from the racemic mixture and this led to the development of the L-isomer as levamisole.

Figure 2. Chemical structures of R (+)-tetramisole (A) and S (-)-tetramisole (levamisole) (B).

From [82].

Tetrahydropyrimidines

This anthelmintic drug class include pyrantel, oxantel and morantel (Figure 3). Pyrantel is an imidazothiazole-derived tetrahydropyrimidine that was discovered in 1966 as an anthelmintic agent with broad spectrum activity against roundworms and hookworms in domestic animals [88,89].

Figure 3. Chemical structures of pyrantel (A), morantel (B) and oxantel (C). From [89].

Macrocyclic lactones (MLs)

Macrocyclic lactones (avermectins and milbemycins) are a group of chemical compounds derived from soil microorganisms of the genus *Streptomyces* [78]. MLs were introduced in the 1980s as antiparasitic agents with broad spectrum activity against nematodes and arthropods. Examples of commercially available avermectins are ivermectin, abamectin, doramectin and selamectin, while milbemycin oxime and moxidectin, are examples of commercially available milbemycins.

Figure 4. Chemical structures of ivermectin (A), abamectin (B), milbemycin D (C) and moxidectin (D). From ^[92].

Amino-acetonitrile derivatives (AADs)

The AADs are a new class of synthetic anthelmintics with broad spectrum activity against nematodes that are resistant to the benzimidazoles, imidazothiazoles and macrocyclic lactones ^[85-88]. Monepantel, also known as AAD 1556, is the first member of this class to be developed for the control of a broad range of parasitic nematodes in sheep (Figure 5) ^[79].

Figure 5. Chemical structure of monepantel. From ^[75].

Spiroindoles

Derquantel (2-deoxy-paraherquamide or PNU-141962) is the first semi-synthetic member of this new class of anthelmintics (Figure 6) ^[81,82]. Derquantel which is also the first commercial member of the spiroindoles, was introduced in 2010 for use in combination with the macrocyclic lactone, abamectin, under the trade name STARTECT[®], for the control of parasitic nematodes in sheep.

Figure 6. Chemical structure of derquantel. From ^[89].

Cyclooctadepsipeptides

Cyclooctadepsipeptides were discovered in the early 1990s. In 1992, PF1022A, the parent compound, was isolated from the fungus, *Mycelia sterilia*, which grows on the leaves of the plant, *Camellia japonica* [91]. PF1022A is made up of four N-methyl-L-leucine, two D-lactate and two D-phenyllactate residues that are arranged as a cyclic octadepsipeptide with an alternating L-D-L configuration (Figure 7) [92].

Figure 7. Chemical structures of PF1022A (A) and emodepside (B). From [94].

Tribendimidine

Tribendimidine is a symmetrical diamidine derivative of amidantel (Figure 8) [89]. It was developed in the mid 1980s by the National Institute of Parasitic diseases in

Shanghai, China, as a broad spectrum anthelmintic drug [77]. In 2004, tribendimidine was approved by the Chinese Food and Drug Administration for treatment of helminth infections in humans [82]. It is the only new anthelmintic drug that has been approved for human use within the past 3 decades [84].

Figure 8. Chemical structures of amidantel (A) and tribendimidine (B). From [88].

Ref:

A BRIEF REVIEW ON THE MODE OF ACTION OF ANTINEMATODAL DRUGS

ABONGWA Melanie, MARTIN Richard J., ROBERTSON Alan P.

Table 1. Anthelmintic resistance and mechanisms of resistance to the major anthelmintic drug classes. Modified from ^[84-88].

Anthelmintic class	Host	Year of initial approval	Year of first published report of resistance	Potential mechanism of resistance
Benzimidazoles				Mutations in β -tubulin;
Thiabendazole	Sheep	1961	1964	Phe200Try, Phe167Try
	Horse	1962	1965	or Glu198Ala
Imidothiazoles-tetrahydropyrimidines				Changes in nicotinic acetylcholine receptors
Levamisole	Sheep	1970	1979	
Pyrantel	Horse	1974	1996	
Avermectin-mylbemicins				Reduced sensitivity of GluCl/GABA receptors
Ivermectin	Sheep	1981	1988	
	Horse	1983	2002	
Moxidectin	Sheep	1991	1995	
	Horse	1995	2003	

Ref:

A BRIEF REVIEW ON THE MODE OF ACTION OF ANTINEMATODAL DRUGS

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Chapter 2

Aim of the Review

The major NTDs prevalent in Bangladesh are Lymphatic Filariasis, Kala-azar and Soil Transmitted Helminthiasis, prevalent in 34, 45 and 64 of 64 districts respectively. The rural population of Bangladesh has traditionally depended on folk medicinal healers for treatment of their ailments. These healers use medicinal plants as their primary source of medicinal formulations. Moreover, the rural people of Bangladesh lack access to modern medicinal facilities. The traditional healers use medicinal plants for treatment and are considered experts in their knowledge of plants and their preparation in disease-treating formulations. (Ref: **1.A Situation Analysis: Neglected Tropical Diseases in Bangladesh December 2010** -Ministry of Health & Family Welfare, Government of Bangladesh)

Medicinal plants were the potent source of many pharmacological activities. Among that the plants of anthelmintic action has attained a great interest due the capability of the plant and its compound to treat a disease that causes major economic loss and reduced livestock production to the livestock holders. The pathogenic infection causes the severe effect of mortality and other problems that were uncontrolled due to the anthelmintic resistance that is developed in the host organism. Even though, many synthetic drugs were manufactured; they produce more side effect than that of the treatment efficacy. Hence, the need for the exploration of the plants for the treatment has attained a great interest and this review gives the list of few medicinal plants that were capable of reducing the helmintic infection.

So, a comparison between various Natural anthelmintics will help us to achieve a better treatment and lower side-effects to the body. In this review we are going to discuss anthelmintic efficacy a few important plants and their easier methods of taking as a herbal medicine. We are also going to highlight the parts that are mostly used for natural anthelmintics.

Chapter 3
Traditional Medicinal Plants
For Treating Helmintic
infections

Syzygium Aromaticum

Plant Profile:

Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Order: Myrtales

Family: Myrtaceae

Genus: Syzygium

Species: *S. aromaticum*

Other Names

English name: Clove

Bengali name: Laung/Lavanga

Habitant: Cloves are the dried flower buds of an aromatic tree are used as spice. Cloves are now harvested primarily in Indonesia , Madagascar , Pakistan, Sri Lanka, India and Bangladesh.

Parts Used: Various parts such as leaves, roots, seeds and dried bud.

Phyto-chemical Constituents :

The phytochemical testing of clove bud showed that clove bud contains **Flavonoid, Saponin, Alkaloid, Tannin** . Clove bud oil typically consists of around 89% of the **phenylpropene eugenol** 6% **eugenyl acetate**, 1.5% **β -caryophyllene**, and many other trace compounds.

Eugenol

Fig: Eugenol the major constituents for anthelmintic effect

Anthelmintic Activity:

A study was evaluated of the anthelmintic activity of alcoholic extract of *Eugenia caryophyllus* & *Uncaria gambier* by using *pheritima posthuma* as a test worms. Both test sample taken at different concentration clove bud extract having (5,10,15 mg/ml conc.) & pale catechu having (50,100,150mg/ml conc.) were tested on indian earth worms (*pheritima posthuma*), paralysis time & death of time were consider as assessment of anthelmintic activity. The albendazole 20mg/ml & normal saline solution were used as a standard & control respectively.

It was noticed in this investigation that the time of paralysis & death of worms was dose dependent & it was much earlier in case of eugenia caryophylus than in gambier catechu.

The result obtained in present investigation is indicating that the clove bud & pale catechu extract showing dose dependent response i.e. from loss of motility to death of worms. In case of test sample of clove bud 15mg/ml conc. showed Paralysis at 1.5 mins. and death occurred within 9.5 mins. In case of pale catechu test sample 150mg/ml conc. Paralysis occurred at 2.5mins. and death occurred within 62.5 mins. So these all finding shown that alcoholic test sample showed significant anthelmintic

activity in a dose dependent manner . At higher concentration showed haemorrhagic spot on the body of the worms. The comparative evaluation of both drugs shows that Clove has potent anthelmintic activity as compared to Pale catechu. Clove oil effectively inhibited the growth of the intestinal parasite *Giardia lamblia*. Clove oil was also found to inhibit the growth of *Trypanosoma cruzi*, the parasite that causes **Chaga's disease**. Clove was found to successfully inhibit *T. cruzi*, with 50% of cells inhibited at 57.5 micrograms/ml and 5 ± 1.06 minutes at 20 mg/ml.

Ref:

1.Aromatherapy Research Article March 2015 Clove Bud Oil

2.IN VITRO ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITY OF SYZYGIUM AROMATICUM FLORAL BUDS AND CINNAMOMUM ZEYLANICUM BARK AQUEOUS EXTRACTS P. LAKSHMI KUMARI, A. SUJITHA AND N. MAHAMMAD RAFI

3.COMPARATIVE ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITY OF EUGENIA CARYOPHYLLUS & UNCARIA GAMBIER

*Manisha Yogesh Sonalkar, Sachin Annasaheb Nitave

Ocimum Sanctum Linn

Plant Profile:

Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Order: Lamiales

Family: Lamiaceae

Genus: *Ocimum*

Binomial name: *Ocimum sanctum* L.

Other Names

English name: Holy Basil.

Bengali name: Tulsi.

Habitant: Which is native to the Indian subcontinent and widespread as a cultivated plant throughout the Southeast Asian tropics.

Parts Used: leaves, stem, flower, root, seeds and even whole plant.

Phyto-chemical Constituents :

The stem and leaves of holy basil contain a variety of constituents that may have biological activity, including saponins, flavonoids, triterpenoids, and tannins. The leaf volatile oil contains eugenol (1-hydroxy-2-methoxy-4-allylbenzene), euginal (also called eugenic acid), urosolic acid (2,3,4,5,6,6a,7,8,8a,,10,11,12,13,14b-tetradecahydro-1H-picene-4a-carboxylic acid, carvacrol (5-isopropyl-2-methylphenol), linalool (3,7-dimethylocta-1,6-dien-3-ol), limatrol, caryophyllene (4,11,11-trimethyl-8-methylene-bicyclo[7.2.0]undec-4-ene), methyl carvicol (also called Estragol: 1-allyl-4-methoxybenzene).

Anthelmintic Activity

The suspension of aqueous extract of leaves of *Ocimum sanctum* Linn, concentration 100 mg/ml was prepared. Albendazole was used as standard reference drug and its 20 mg/ml concentration was prepared by as per the prescribed method. The anthelmintic activity was performed according to standard screening methods. Aqueous extract of *Ocimum sanctum* took 145 ± 14 minutes to paralyze and 223 ± 11 minutes to death of the worm, whereas Albendazole took 92 ± 18 minutes to paralyze and 165 ± 17 minutes to death of the worm with significant ($P < 0.05$) value. Aqueous extract is more potent than control (NS) and lesser antihelmintic activity than albendazole. Time to paralysis and consequent death were significantly higher in aqueous extract of *Ocimum* than that of

Albendazole at same concentrations. Aqueous extract of *Ocimum sanctum* Linn is more potent than control (NS) and lesser anthelmintic activity than albendazole. Time to paralysis and consequent death were significantly higher in aqueous extract of *Ocimum* than that of Albendazole at same concentrations.

Ref:

Anthelmintic Activity of Tulsi Leaves (*Ocimum Sanctum* Linn)–An In-Vitro Comparative Study Madhavulu Buchineni ,Rama Mohan Pathapati, Jithendra Kandati

Azadirachta indica

Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Order: Sapindales

Family: Meliaceae

Genus: *Azadirachta*

Species: *A.indica*

Other Names

English name: 'Indian Lilac' or 'Margosa' *A. Indica*

Bengali name: Neem

Habitant: It is one of two species in the genus of *Azadirachta*. It is native to India, Bangladesh, Thailand, Nepal and Pakistan. It grows well in tropical and sub-tropical regions. In India, Neem is known as “the village pharmacy” because of its healing versatility. The tree has been used in Ayurvedic medicine due to its medicinal properties.

Parts Used: All parts of the plant including the leaves, bark, fruits, seed, oil and sap have been shown to have medicinal properties and contain over ten different active components with azadirachtin as the most potent and widely studied.

Chemical Constituents:

Anthelmintic Activity:

A trial was conducted for 63 days in non-descript kids to assess the efficacy of feeding Neem leaves as an anthelmintic source. Twelve weaned non-descript male kids (approximately 8-9 months old) were used in the study. The animals were dewormed and dipped for ecto-parasites. Four kids were randomly allotted to each of the following three treatments that were fed with complete diet having iso-nitrogenous and iso-caloric value. The animals were experimentally infected on day one of the experiment with 5000 larvae of *Haemonchus contortus*(L3) cultured as mentioned earlier in the following manner.

- | | | |
|---|---|--|
| Control group (T1) | - | Complete rations without Neem leaves and without infection with <i>Haemonchus contortus</i> (L3) |
| Infected group (T2) | - | Complete rations without Neem leaves and infected with <i>Haemonchus contortus</i> (L3) |
| Infected and Neem leaves fed group (T3) | - | Complete rations with Neem leaves and challenged with <i>Haemonchus contortus</i> (L3) |

The Average Daily Gain (ADG) of the three groups was 43.33, 22.86 and 25.87 g, respectively. The ADG of kids in T1 was significantly higher ($p < 0.01$) compared to T2 and T3. Though the Neem leaves fed groups (T3) had a higher ADG of 3 g compared to control challenged group, it was not statistically significant. Average EPG count of *Haemonchus contortus* in the dung of goats experimentally infected with *Haemonchus contortus* L3 larvae or without infection in a trial conducted to evaluate the anthelmintic effect of Neem leaves. The EPG count between T2 and T3 were not statistically significant at 21st, 28th and 35th day post-infection where as it was highly significant ($p < 0.01$) from 42nd day onwards.

DISCUSSION

Similar to 1000 µg concentration of azadirachtin, inhibition of motility of *Haemonchus contortus* larvae was observed by Assis *et al.* (2003) at higher concentrations of plant extracts of hexane and methanol indicating the relevance of this screening test in judging anthelmintic property.

Ref:

- 1. Anthelmintic efficacy of neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) and the homeopathic product Fator Vermes1 in Morada Nova sheep** A.C.S. Chagas a, L.S. Vieira , A.R. Freitas , M.R.A. Araujo , J.A. Araujo-Filho , W.R. Araguaño , A.M.C. Navarro
- 2. Evaluation of Anthelmintic Effect of Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaves on *Haemonchus contortus* in Goats-** L.Radhakrishnan, S.Gonathinayagan and V.Balakrishnan
- 3. Evaluation of Anthelmintic Effect of Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaves on *Haemonchus contortus* in Goats-** L.Radhakrishnan, S.Gonathinayagan and V.Balakrishnan

Carica papaya Linn.

Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Order: Brassicales

Family: Caricaceae

Genus: Carica

Species: *C. papaya*

Other Names

Botanical Name: Carica papaya

Family Name: Caricaceae

Common Name: Papaya, Paw Paw, Kates, Papaw.

Habitant:

The places that are the most successful at commercially growing these plants include Hawaii, tropical Africa, the Philippines, India, Ceylon, Malaya and Australia.

Parts Used: Leaves, Fruits, bark, seeds, root, peel.

Chemical Constituents:

Anthelmintic Activity:

Chloroform extract of the seeds of *C. papaya* during the acute phase with doses of 50 mg/kg, 75 mg/kg and 100 mg/kg of a mixture of the major fatty acid components (stearic acid, palmitic acid and oleic acid) showed antiprotozoal activity against trypomastigotes of *T. cruzi*, however total elimination of the parasites was not observed with any of the doses tested. With the crude chloroform extract at doses of 50 and 75 mg/kg, a reduction in the number of parasites of 54 and 54% respectively was observed compared with the positive control (allopurinol 8.5 mg/kg) and animals treated with the mixture of compounds showed a 40% reduction when were compared with the positive control group. The 50 and 75 mg/kg doses also exhibited an antiprotozoal activity increase throughout the experiment to be below the negative control group (35 and 34% respectively).

Effect of *C. papaya* extract (at doses of 50 and 75 µg/g) and the mix of fatty acids identified in the crude extract (at doses of 100, 200 and 300) on the mortality rate of BALB/c mice infected with *T. cruzi* and treated during 28 days.

In this study shows that the chloroform extract of *C. papaya* has significant anthelmintic activity, but does not totally eliminate *T. cruzi* trypomastigotes during the active phase of infection. However, this is a promising potential drug to use associated with other commonly used anti-*T. cruzi* drugs, such as benznidazol, for improving therapeutic effectiveness.

Nigella sativa

Taxonomic classification

Kingdom: Plantae
Subkingdom: Tracheobionta
Superdivision: Spermatophyta
Phylum: Magnoliophyta
Class: Magnoliopsida
Order : Ranunculales
Family: Ranunculaceae
Genus: Nigella
Species : N. sativa

Common names : Black cumin, Fennel Flower, Nutmeg Flower, Black seed, Black Caraway, Roman Coriander, Damascena, Devil in-the-bush, Wild Onion Seed.

Habitant: N. sativa is native to Southern Europe, North Africa and Southwest Asia and it is cultivated in many countries in the world like Middle Eastern Mediterranean region, South Europe, India, Pakistan, Syria, Turkey, Saudi Arabia and Bangladesh.

Parts Used: Various parts such as leaves, roots, seeds.

Chemical Constituents:

CARVONE

THYMOQUINONE

THYMOL

NIGELLICINE

NIGELLICIMINE

NIGELLICIMINE N-OXIDE

Table : Some major chemical constituents present in *N. sativa*

Anthelmintic Activity:

Dwarf tapeworm (*Hymenolepis nana*, also known as *Rodentolepis nana*, *Vampirolepis nana*, *Hymenolepis fraterna*, and *Taenia nana*) is a cosmopolitan species though most common in temperate zones, and is one of the most common cestodes (a type of intestinal worm or helminth) infecting humans, especially children.

In conclusion, the results of the present study reinforced the effectiveness of *N. sativa* oil as effective treatment against *H. nana* through experimental study on the white laboratory mice.

Ref:

Assessment of the Anti-Protozoal Activity of Crude Carica papaya Seed Extract against Trypanosoma cruzi Matilde Jiménez-Coello , Eugenia Guzman-Marín , Antonio Ortega-Pacheco , Salud Perez-Gutiérrez and Karla Y. Acosta-Viana.

Punica grantum Linn

BOTANICAL CLASSIFICATION

Botanical name- Punica granatum

Kingdom: Plantae (Angiosperms)

Order: Myrtales

Family: Lythraceae

Genus: Punica

Species: P. granatum

Other Names

Hindi : Anar,

English : Pomegranate,

Bengali : Dadim,

Habitant: It is widely cultivated throughout the Middle East and Caucasus region, north and tropical Africa, the Indian subcontinent, Central Asia, the drier parts of southeast Asia, and parts of the Mediterranean Basin.^[3] It is also cultivated in parts of Arizona and California.

Parts Used: Various parts such as leaves, fruit rinds, bark and roots.

Chemical Constituents:

Anthelmintic Activity:

The worms used in the in-vitro assay are *Pheretima posthuma*, *Ascaridia galli*, *Ascaris lumbricoids*, *Raillietina spiralis*.

Table : Anthelmintic activity of peel extracts of *Punica granatum Linn.*

Sr. no	Test Extract of <i>Punica granatum L.</i>	Concentration (mg/ml)	Time of paralysis in min. (Mean)	Time of Death In min. (Mean)
1	Aqueous extract of fruit peel	25(mg/ml)	66	86
		50(mg/ml)	44	69
		100(mg/ml)	24	65
		150(mg/ml)	14	37

2	Ethanolic extract of fruit peel	25(mg/ml)	50	62
		50(mg/ml)	37	48
		100(mg/ml)	24	39
		150(mg/ml)	12	23
3	Methanolic extract of fruit peel	25(mg/ml)	34	25
		50(mg/ml)	26	18
		100(mg/ml)	18	15
		150(mg/ml)	9	12

The experimental data it was found that aqueous, ethanol and methanol extract from peel of *punica granatum Linn.* shows anthelmintic activity against earth worm. Dose dependant activity was observed in all three extracts as shown in table.

The time of paralysis and death was noted against various concentrations of extracts. The time for paralysis of earth worm for aqueous, ethanol and methanol at low concentration (25 mg/ml) was 66, 50 and 34 minutes respectively and at high concentration (150 mg/ml) was 14, 12 and 09 minutes respectively. Death time for aqueous, ethanol and methanol at low concentration (25 mg/ml) was 86, 62, 25 minutes and at high concentration (150 mg/ml) 37, 23 and 12 minutes respectively.

Ref:

1. **Nigella Sativa Linn- A Comprehensive Review**-Padmaa M Paarakh

2. **Efficacy of Black Seeds Oil (Nigella sativa) against Hymenolepis nana in Infected Mice**

Wafa A. I. Al-Megrin.

3. **ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITY OF NIGELLA SATIVA L., SEEDS ON GASTROINTESTINAL NEMATODES OF SHEEP**

I.R.M. AL-SHAIBANI M.S. PHULAN, A. ARIJO, T.A. QURESHI* AND A.M. KUMBHER

Mimusops elengi

Taxonomical Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Order : Ericales

Family : Sapotaceae

Genus : Mimusops

Species : M. elengi L

Other Names

English: bullet wood, spanish cherry;

Hindi: mulsari, sinha kasaraka

Bengali: Bakul.

Habitant: Harvested primarily in Indonesia , India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka,India and Bangladesh.

Parts Used: Various parts such as Stem bark, leaves, flowers, fruit and seed.

Chemical Constituents :

Some major constituents in M.elengi

Phytochemical review shows the presence of taraxerol, taraxerone, ursolic acid, betulinic acid, α -spinosterol, β -sitosterol, lupeol, alkaloid isoretronecyl tiglate and mixture of triterpenoid saponins in the bark of *Mimusops elengi*.

Anthelmintic activity:

In vitro anthelmintic activity of crude **alcoholic extract and its ethyl acetate and n-butanol fractions** of *M. elengi* bark (70 % alcoholic extract) and its different fractions against *Pheretima posthuma* and *Ascardia galli*.

Active principles such as taraxerol, taraxerone, ursolic acid, betulinic acid, Alpha-spinosterol, Beta-sitosterol, alkaloid, isoretronecyl tiglate and mixture of triterpenoid, saponins have been reported from its stem bark. Crude alcoholic extract and its various fractions were evaluated for their anthelmintic potential using *Pheretima posthuma* (Annelida) and *A scardia galli* (Nematode) as test worms. The crude alcoholic extract and its ethyl acetate and n-butanol fractions significantly demonstrated paralysis and also cause death of worms especially at higher concentration of 100mg/ml as compared to standard reference Piperazine citrate (10mg/ml). The activity was attributed to the presence of polyphenolic compound and tannins in the stem bark.

Tannins are believed to interfere with energy generation in helminth parasites by uncoupling oxidative phosphorylation and could bind to glycoprotein on the cuticle of the parasite thereby may cause death.

Ref:

A Review on Anthelmintic Plants- Ravindra G M ali and Anita A Mehta

Chapter 4

Comparison Study

Name	Family	Usable parts of plant	How to use	Competitive inhibition	Disease (Most frequently treated)
Syzygium Aromaticum (Clove)	Myrtaceae	Dried bud, stems and leaves	Herbal tea /Decoction	Alcoholic extract of dried clove buds showed death of <i>P. posthuma</i> in concentration of 15mg/ml .	Chaga's Disease, lymphatic filariasis
Ocimum Sanctum (Tulsi)	Lamiaceae	Leaf oil extract	Herbal tea /Decoction	Aqueous extract of <i>Ocimum sanctum</i> -223+11 minutes to death of the worm ($p < 0.05$) in 100mg/ml.	Giardia, Leishmania, Ascariasis
Azadirachta Indica (Neem)	Meliaceae	Leaf oil	Herbal tea /Decoction	Neem leaves extract-1000mg on <i>haemonchus contortus</i> for (91-97)% larvae affected.	Haemonchosis
Carica Papaya (Papaya)	Cariaceae	Leaf, seed, root	Decoction /Fresh juice	crude chloroform extract at doses of 50 and 75 mg/kg, a reduction in the number of parasites of 54 and 54% respectively	Chaga's Disease
Nigella Sativa (Black cumin)	Caryophyllaceae	Seed oil	Herbal tea /Decoction	<i>N. sativa</i> oil lead to highly reduce eggs passed per gram of faeces by using does 5ml/kg. However, using dose 2.5ml/kg show efficacy reached to 100% by day 21.	schistosomiasis
Punica grantum (Pomegranate)	Lythraceae	Seed oil Peel	Decoction /Fresh juice	Aquous, methanolic, ethanolic extract of fruit peel showed on 150 mg/ml death of worms in 12 minutes.	Ascariasis
Mimusops elengi (Bakul)	Sapotaceae	Stem, bark, Seeds	Decoction /Gargle	Methanolic extract-100mg/ml caused death of worms.	Ascariasis

Table: Comparison between different plants with anthelmintic efficacy.

Fig.1: Graphical representation showing most used preparation of anthelmintic plants

Fig.2: The distribution of plant organs used in traditional medicine for the treatment of parasite

Fig .3:Graph showing efficacy of various medicinal herbs as Anthelmintics

Fig .4:Graph showing frequency of herbal preparation methods(Ref:14)

Chapter 5

Conclusion

Traditional system of medicine is one of the age-old practices and humans have postulated and ultimately established this system, in particular, the usage of traditional medicinal plants through empirical observation and by trial and error experiment. There are many thorny issues and daunting challenges that need to be addressed effectively and immediately for the promotion of traditional medicinal plants. The collaborative efforts of ethnobotanists, anthropologists, pharmacists, and physicians could be a workable strategy to evaluate and validate the usage custom of traditional medicinal plants with the existing modern scientific methods and innovative techniques. From our personal observation, being born and brought up in developing countries like Bangladesh, especially from the rural underprivileged section of the society, we have experienced that the sick primarily approach the proximate traditional healer who is the primary health care provider in that area. Subsequently, they may travel to the adjacent modern (allopathy) health facilities if they do not get completely cured by the former. ^[116].

In true sense, our traditional knowledge on medicinal plants plays a major role, especially in developing countries, and helps the rural poor to lead a healthier and disease-free life. Based on the existing data for the betterment of traditional medicinal plants practice and future prospects, the present review makes the following recommendations: Recommendations In developing countries, a sizable fraction of the rural poor still depends on traditional herbal medicine; however, the efficiency and the intrinsic compounding factors are still unknown and imprecise, which needs to be scientifically validated by conducting more detailed antimicrobial assays.

Many believe that phytotherapeutic agents are quite safe; nevertheless, a few of them might have intrinsic toxicity too. There is a possibility of contamination or adulteration, and so these should be administered with great care and under the supervision of herbalist. Human safety must be determined by conducting standardized scientific clinical trials. In several instances, the administered herbal medicinal products' dosage is unknown or imprecise, which may lead to severe adverse side effects. Therefore, the desirable and appropriate dosage level must be determined by conducting more scientific experiments. ^[109,110].

Education programs such as short courses on modern traditional medicine or exposure to the subject in the undergraduate curriculum will be of benefit and will awareness among health care practitioners. Special herbal system of medicinal units should be established within the premises of the modern health facilities, which would offer the opportunity to the patients to acquire traditional medicine, based on their personal interest. Worldwide, conservation of traditional medicinal plants is a matter of grave concern. The well-known traditional *Materia Medica* should be protected and

preserved by employing various projects to realize the plant conservation for our future need^[109].

Traditional practitioners in the study area mostly used leaves (29.8%) for preparation of remedies followed by roots . The preference of leaves for remedial preparation is due to safety to use and make sure the plants sustainability and to prevent extinction. **Abiyu Enyew et al.** also suggested that, leaves are easily renewal part and their utilization may not put medicinal plants at risk of extinction. Some other researchers also observed that, leaves were commonly used plant parts for remedial preparation in their study area. Most traditional remedies (50.3%) were prepared by using fresh materials. This may be related to the availability of active compounds in fresh materials compared to dried one. Abiyu Enyew et al also suggested that, biologically active principles in fresh leaves may degrade up on drying. To support the present findings, many ethnobotanical investigators reported that most remedies were prepared from fresh plant materials. In the study area, common preparation methods of remedies was extracting juice by squeezing (24.9%) followed by powdering (16.6%). Preparing remedies by squeezing is advantageous over using decoction since heat may affect the active principles of the remedies. To improve the quality of ethnomedicine and also acceptability by the patient, remedies were mixed with water, sugar, butter, milk, honey, tea or coffee and given for drinking, chewing or eating^[110].

Herbal drugs and its importance

In the recent years, the importance of Herbal drugs in Medicine has tremendously increased because of their fewer side effects. Consequently, the demand for the herbal formulation is increasing day by day. The phytochemical constituents and their standardization are accelerated with the development of instrumental analysis and this field becomes important and new for investigation. As the half of world suffering from bacterial and Helminthes infection, the source of infection being very common due to poor sanitation, poor family hygiene, malnutrition, and crowded living conditions.

The sources of infections are:

- 1) Human being: The commonest source of infection is human being themselves.
- 2) Animals: Many pathogens are able to infect both human being and animals. Animals act as source of human infection.
- 3) Insects: Blood sucking insect may transmit pathogen to human beings. Besides acting as vector, some insect may also act as a reservoir for hosts.

4) Soil and water: Some pathogens can survive in the soil for very long periods. Water may act as the source of infection either due to contamination with pathogenic microorganism or due to presence of aquatic vector.

5) Food: Contaminated food act as a source of infection.

So there is a need to develop antibacterial and anthelmintics drug from herbal source. Anthelmintic activity was carried out by measuring the time for paralysis of worm. [116].

Chapter 6

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